

CASHLESS POLICY AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: ACHIEVING SDG-8

Oluwasogo Adediran, Ph.D¹, Oluwasegun Adekoya^{2*}

¹Department of Economics and Development Studies, Covenant University, Nigeria.

oluwasogo.adediran@covenantuniversity.edu.ng

²Department of Economics and Development Studies, Covenant University, Nigeria.

Oluwasegun.adekoyapgs@stu.cu.edu.ng

*Corresponding Author's email: Oluwasegun.adekoyapgs@stu.cu.edu.ng

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Abstract

The Nigerian government introduced the cashless policy to modernize the payment system and achieve Vision 2020's goal of becoming a top 20 global economy. However, by 2020, Nigeria ranked 26th in GDP. With expanding digital infrastructure, adopting the cashless policy remains crucial for economic growth and achieving SDGs 1, 2, 8, and 9 by 2030. This study examines its impact using secondary data from 1991 to 2022, analyzed with the ARDL model. Findings reveal a statistically significant positive relationship between economic growth and the cashless policy, facilitated by technology. The study recommends government investment in structural development and improved accessibility of digital banking platforms to enhance financial inclusion and economic progress.

Keywords: Cashless, Economic Growth, Financial Inclusion, Technology

1. INTRODUCTION

Internet banking and mobile banking have revolutionized Nigeria's business environment, with the cashless policy being implemented in Lagos state in 2012. This policy aims to modernize the payment system, enhance efficiency, and curb corruption (CBN, 2012). It was further launched in six other states which are Anambra, Ogun, Rivers, Abia, the Federal Capital Territory, and Kano in 2013 and national implementation began in July 2014. The policy applies to all financial accounts, except government income-generating accounts, lending institutions, microfinance banks, and embassies. The cashless policy was initially announced in 1996 however implementation began in 2012 which aimed for gradual take-off and nationwide compliance, overcoming challenges such as digitization. (Chukwuma, Chris & Martins, 2020).

A cashless economy is an economic environment in which money used for transitional purposes is being spent without being physically carried from a transitional location to another (Adu, 2016). In Nigeria, the adoption of the cashless policy is a giant step towards realizing its economic potential. The policy was introduced to align with Nigeria's Vision 2020 goal of ranking among the top 20 economies by 2020. It aims to lower the cost associated with bank services, promote financial inclusion, and enhance the effectiveness of the Central Bank's monetary policy.

This policy also aims to curb inflation and drive economic growth (CBN, 2012). Nigeria is transitioning towards a cashless economy, driven by economic agents like individuals, firms, financial institutions, fintech companies, and the government. The CBN reports that the inclusion rate has increased from 47.0% in 2012 to 64.1% by 2020, indicating increased financial inclusion and job creation in Point-of-Sale businesses (CBN, 2020). However, challenges such as cybersecurity concerns, failed transactions, fraudulent activities, infrastructural gaps, and a digital divide hinder the full realization of the cashless policy.

There is an onward movement towards achieving Sustainable Development Goals 1, 2, 8 and 9 which are no poverty, zero hunger, decent work and economic growth, and industry, innovation and infrastructure. The adoption of the cashless policy towards attainment of economic growth can be a catalyst in achieving these SDGs goals by promoting financial inclusion which ensures that more people have access to services provided by financial institutions which aligns with reducing poverty (SDG 1) and gradually attains a zero hunger zone (SDG 2) which in turn fosters economic growth (SDG 8) when the welfare of the citizens improve with employment generation into the financial system via the Point of Sale operators who facilitate financial transactions with a given charge which curbs the waiting time at banks. The adoption of the cashless policy also drives innovation and infrastructural development (SDG 9) as technologies are used to facilitate the reality of a move towards a cashless economy.

In the light of the above, there are potential benefits of an economy going cashless especially in the current state the global economy is, which informs a study into this relationship. Hence, this study examines the impact of cashless policy driven by technology development on economic growth in Nigeria stating that, there is a driver that needs to push this potential beneficial impact which other studies have critically overlooked in their study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Tran and Wang (2023) investigated cashless payment's impact on economic growth: evidence in G20 countries and Vietnam. The countries investigated for the purpose of this study are Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, Korea, Mexico, Russia, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Turkey, United Kingdom, United States, European Union and Vietnam. The study utilized annual data from various sources, including the World Bank, Bank for International Settlements, State Bank of Vietnam, and the World Government Index, to analyze the impact of cashless payment on Vietnam's economic growth. The dependent variable was Real GDP growth rate, while the independent variables were debit card transaction value, credit card transaction value, E-Money transaction value, and check transaction value. The control variables included inflation rate, population growth rate, secondary school enrollment, and trade openness. The results showed a robust relationship between economic growth and cashless payment, despite controlling for endogeneity, omitted variables, and outliers. This study however is criticized for not taking into account a potential driver that aids the facilitation of cashlessness which this study incorporates as technology development.

Noman, Maydybura, Channa, Wong and Chang (2023) carried out a study on the impact of cashless bank payment on economic growth: evidence from G7 countries which were Canada, Germany, Japan, France, Italy, the United Kingdom and the United States. The study used secondary data from the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) and World Bank economic database to examine the relationship between cashless bank payment and economic growth from year period 2010 to 2020. The dependent variable was Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and the independent variables were credit transfer transactions, cheque payment transactions, and Card & E-Money transactions. The Panel Autoregressive - Distributed Lag (ARDL) was used to analyze the relationship between these variables. The findings showed a positive relationship in both short and long run, but credit transfer had an insignificant relationship with Real GDP however, in the study of (Tran & Wang, 2023), the result is negative given the difference in economic structure and degree of pressure that emanates from the difference in technologies.

In Nigeria, there has been various studies that have been done to examine the impact and relationship that exist between cashless policy on the nation's economic growth and development. To begin with, Ogunlade and Amodu (2024) determined the influence cashless policy has on economic growth and development in Nigeria. The study used primary data from a structured questionnaire to analyze the correlation between cashless policy and economic growth and development in Nigeria. The target population consisted of ten selected deposit money banks, with 181 questionnaires retrieved out of 200 sent out. The independent variables were Electronic Banking System, Electronic Transfer System, and Peer-To-Peer payment. The findings showed a significant positive impact of cashless policy on economic growth and development. This study has failed to capture a key variable that facilitates the efficient use of these cashless instruments which is technology that could be in form of internet connectivity or a secure internet server.

A study on the impact of cashless policy on the economic growth of Nigeria was done by (Chukwuma *et al.*, 2020). The study employed the use of secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, Nigeria Stock Exchange Fact book and Exchange Commission database which covered year 2013 to 2019 given the availability of data as at the time the study was carried out. For the purpose of analysis, and the variables used were Automated teller Machine (ATM), Point of Sale, Mobile and Internet Banking with Real GDP. The study however had no analytical content but used historical findings to form the basis for impact analysis which had a mix of various variables. The conclusion from the study reveals that determination on the kind of impact cashless policy has on economic growth cannot be ascertained.

Ehiedu, Oditia and Kifordu (2020) embarked on a study on cashless policy model and Nigeria economic growth. The study investigates the impact of Automated Teller Machines (ATM) on money laundering activities in Nigeria and the relationship between Point of Sale (POS) and employment opportunities. Results show ATM reduces money laundering, while POS facilitates employment generation, and e-banking services positively impact economic growth in Nigeria. There was no deep connection to show how ATM can effectively reduce money laundering activities in the nation. (Agu & Agu, 2020) study had an examination on the impact of cashless policy on economic growth in Nigeria for year periods 2010-2018 through the use of quarterly time series data sourced from the Central Bank Statistical Bulletin Annual Report and World Bank Development Indicator. The study used the Johansen cointegration test and granger causality test to analyze the impact of cashless policy on Nigeria's economic performance. It found a positive relationship between cheque payment and POS services, while

ATM and online web payment negatively impacted economic growth. However, no significant relationship was found between cheque value and online payment.

What relationship exist between gross fixed capital formation, labour productivity, access to internet and economic growth? The study done by (Topcu, Altinoz & Aslan, 2020) revealed that gross fixed capital formation has a positive relationship with economic growth in the long-run and statistically significant (Kanu & Anayochukwu, 2014) had a finding that in the short-run there exist a positive relationship which is not statistically significant. (Adeshina, Adewale, Elvis & Emile, 2019) examined the relationship between labour and economic growth and found out that there exist a positive relationship and it is not statistically significant. However, in a previous study carried out by (Jajri & Ismail, 2010) the findings revealed that there exists a positive relationship which is also statistically significant. Access to internet has been on the rise in recent times with individuals getting to use digital platforms to transact on a daily basis, to this end what kind of relationship could exist between individual access to internet and economic growth? (Meah, 2012) whose study was on the impact of internet on economic growth in Bangladesh unveiled through his findings that there exists a positive relationship between the two variables which is not statistically significant. Moreover, studies years after done by (Abdulqadir & Asongu, 2022; Edquist, Goodridge & Haskel, 2021) has established that there exists a positive relationship which is also statistically significant.

For the purpose of this study, the Finance-Led Growth Theory will be employed. The Finance-Led Growth Theory is a theoretical postulation that the development of the financial sector of any country is a key driver of economic growth which is traced to the origin of Schumpeter theory. This theory further hypothesizes that a financial system that is developed facilitates efficient resource allocation, mobilizes savings, supports investment which are all crucial factors for economic development. The Finance-Led Growth Theory lays emphasis on the relevance of financial markets and intermediaries in directing funds from savers to borrowers which ultimately promotes capital formation, stirs up technological innovation and hence, leads to overall economic growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 MODEL SPECIFICATION

The model examines the relationship between cashless policy as it relates to economic growth in Nigeria between 1991 and 2022. The 1991–2022 period is suitable as it captures Nigeria's pre- and post-cashless policy phases. It includes financial reforms, technological advancements, fintech growth, and the 2012 cashless policy launch. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated digital payments, making this timeframe ideal for analyzing the policy's impact on financial inclusion and economic growth. The data were sourced from CBN statistical bulletin, Macrotrends and World Development Indicators. The dependent variable (GR) was used to capture economic growth. It was further measured as a function of independent variables which are CAS, GFC, LAB and INT. This statement in functional form is written as:

$$GR = F(CAS, GFC, LAB, INT) \quad (3.1)$$

Furthermore, it is written as an economic equation based on the specified equation above as:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 W_t + \beta_3 L_t + \beta_4 I_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.2)$$

Where Y: economic growth variable is GR;

X: cashless economy variable is CAS;

W: capital invested variable is GFCF;

L: labour force variable is LAB and

I: Individual access to internet variable is INT.

The equation can further be expressed in linear form as:

$$GR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CAS_t + \beta_2 GFCF_t + \beta_3 LAB_t + \beta_4 INT_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.3)$$

Where:

GR represents Gross Domestic Product Per Capita;

CAS represents Cashless economy;

GFCF represents Gross Fixed Capital Formation;

LAB represents Labour force and

INT represents Individual access to internet.

4. ANALYSIS

For the purpose of this study, the result would be broken down into sections. To begin with, descriptive statistics are provided to give an analytical overview of the mean, standard deviation. Furthermore, a unit root test is conducted to determine the level of stationarity. Lastly, ARDL model is used to perform the analysis for this study and to critically unveil the type of relationships that exist amongst the variables under study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	GR	CAS	GFCF	INT	LAB
Mean	1666.263	7286151	12190.12	14.03841	59.97709
Median	1874.085	7189171	7266.445	6.157518	60.243
Maximum	3200.953	21406250	65227.13	55.4	60.707
Minimum	494.1292	20816.3	285.59	0	58.311
Std. Dev.	802.372	5162680	16231	18.09074	0.64888
Skewness	-0.06612	0.665777	2.073635	1.164116	-1.14483
Kurtosis	1.889494	3.612204	6.551323	3.056481	3.093353
Jarque-Bera	1.667612	2.863772	39.74899	7.231802	7.001666
Probability	0.434393	0.238858	0	0.026893	0.030172
Sum	53320.41	2.33E+08	390083.8	449.2292	1919.267
Sum Sq. Dev.	19957823	8.26E+14	8.17E+09	10145.52	13.05239
Observations	32	32	32	32	32

Source: Authors Computation (2024)

The Table 1 is the descriptive statistics used to analyze the variables in this study. The mean values for GR, CAS, GFCF, LAB, and INT were 1666.233, 7286151, 12190.12, 59.97709, and 14.03841. Skewness was measured to determine the asymmetry of the data distribution. GDP is nearly symmetrical, CAS, GFCF, and INT experience a right-skewed distribution while LAB is left-skewed. Kurtosis is to determine normal distribution if it has a value of 3; GDP is

platykurtic since its value is less than 3, CAS, GFCF are both leptokurtic given values greater than 3 while INT and LAB are close to 3 indicating a normal distribution.

The result from Jargue-Bera probability with a null hypothesis to fail to reject if the p-value is greater than 0.05, indicates that GDP and CAS have no significant deviation from normality.

Table 2: Bound Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	3.976698	10%	2.2	3.09
k	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.50%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37

Source: Authors Computation (2024)

From Table 2. bound test shown, using the 5% significance value, the lower threshold is 2.56 while the upper value is at 3.49. Given the F-statistic value of 3.976698 which is greater than both lower and upper value, there is a likelihood of a long-term stable relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables examined in this study. Hence, it is safe to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a long-term relationship at 5% level of significance.

Table 4: Auto Regressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL)

4.1 Short-Run and Long-run result

Short-Run				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
GR(-1)	0.534132	0.202857	2.633047	0.0174
GR(-2)	0.079603	0.241559	0.329539	0.7458
GR(-3)	-0.28414	0.201795	-1.40808	0.1771
CAS	-3.14E-06	2.49E-05	-0.12619	0.9011
CAS(-1)	3.13E-05	2.46E-05	1.273357	0.22
GFCF	-0.02068	0.021527	-0.96052	0.3503
INT	83.711	26.96465	3.104471	0.0064

LAB	817.4722	615.9413	1.327192	0.202
LAB(-1)	-252.219	741.639	-0.34008	0.738
LAB(-2)	-286.288	768.2706	-0.37264	0.714
LAB(-3)	1694.357	898.3203	1.886138	0.0765
C	-118571	33450.4	-3.54467	0.0025
CointEq(-1)	-0.67041	0.120647	-5.55679	0.0003
R-squared	0.900544	Mean dependent var		1780.673
Adjusted R-squared	0.836191	S.D. dependent var		753.6728
S.E. of regression	305.0365	Akaike info criterion		14.57224
Sum squared resid	1581804	Schwarz criterion		15.13802
Log likelihood	-199.298	Hannan-Quinn criter.		14.74944
F-statistic	13.9937	Durbin-Watson stat		2.228679
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002			
Long-Run				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CAS	4.20E-05	2.46E-05	1.707014	0.106
GFCF	-0.03084	0.02867	-1.07581	0.297
INT	124.8657	26.05928	4.791601	0.0002
LAB	2943.463	822.7145	3.577745	0.0023
C	-176863	49811.86	-3.55062	0.0025

Source: Authors Computation (2024)

The study reveals a strong relationship between the dependent variable (GR) and the independent variables (CAS, GFCF, LAB, and INT) with the R-squared around 90% and an adjusted R-squared of 84%. The F-statistic with a p-value of 0.000002 which is less than the p-value of 0.05, indicates the model's appropriateness for policy-making. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.228679 indicates no autocorrelation

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULT

The long-run estimated model revealed that the constant term which is growth rate in the short-run is negative and statistically significant, with a probability value of 0.0025, this is with the absence of the independent variable contribution. Cashless economy, access to internet which is a proxy for technology and labour had positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria with access to internet and labour being statistically significant while cashless economy is not statistically significant. The impact of gross fixed capital formation on economic growth had

an established negative impact which was insignificant. The study carried out by (Tran & Wang, 2023) revealed that there is a positive relationship between cashless payment and economic growth, while the study of (Ali, 2015; Kanu & Ozurumba, 2019; Topcu, Altinoz & Aslan, 2020) does not align with the result gotten for gross fixed capital formation. (Adeshina et al., 2019) study on labour and economic growth conforms to the findings from the study given the result obtained that labour has a positive relationship with economic growth. The study carried out by (Ji, 2019) concluded that access to internet has a positive impact on economic growth which is supported by (Yin & Choi, 2022). In terms of significance, (Abdulqadir & Asongu, 2022) had a finding that access to internet had a positive impact on economic growth which was also statistically significant. However, the study by (Meah, 2012) revealed that access to internet had a positive impact on economic growth however was not statistically significant.

In the short-run estimate, the optimal log of four was determined using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), which is also known as the Bayesian information Criterion. The given error correction co-efficient explains the speed of adjustment from any distortion that could emerge in the short-run advancing to the long-run. The error correction is -0.60741 and it is statistically significant at 5% confidence. This result aligns to the theory backing up the use of the error correction acceptance that it has to be negative, below one and it should be statistically significant. From the figure, this implies that 67.041% of any disequilibrium is resorted in the first year.

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

The study has examined the impact cashless policy has on economic growth in Nigeria. Nigeria's economic growth has been negatively impacted by the implementation of a cashless policy in 2023, as it led to a decline in business operations and activities. The real GDP increased by 2.31% in Q1 2023, but decreased from 3.11% to 3.52% in Q4 2022. This decline is attributed to the negative impacts of the cash crunch. The study suggests that implementing a cashless economy could potentially aid economic growth in Nigeria, as more financially-informed individuals are expected to contribute to the economy. Nigeria's economic growth is hindered by infrastructure shortfalls in transportation, electricity, and telecommunications, affecting productivity and efficiency. However, investment in skill training, healthcare, social protection programs, and structural reforms can stimulate innovation and boost labor productivity. The internet, enabling informed decision-making and adapting to economic changes, and e-commerce platforms, further boost economic growth.

Recommendation

1. The government should roll out policies that would aid structural development to enable financial inclusion across board and have more individuals gain access to the internet.
2. Banks should work on having their respective digital platforms accessible and user friendly for those who might not be literates in information technology.
3. Establishment of social protection programs, skill acquisition programs, training and development to stimulate labour productivity.

AUTHORS DECLARATION

The authors declare that this study is original, plagiarism free and adhres to ethicl publication standard.

Authors Contribution: Introduction and Literature Review, Oluwasogo Adediran, Methodology, Analysis, Discussion of Result and Conclusion and Implication, Oluwasegun Adekoya.

Data Availability Statement: The data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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